

RESEARCH ARTICLE

ECOFRIENDLY MANAGEMENT OF MAIZE WEEVIL (*SITOPHILUS ZEAMAI*) AS INFLUENCED BY DIFFERENT SPICES POWDER

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ARTICLE DETAILS

ABSTRACT

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The maize weevil (*Sitophilus zeamais* Motschulsky) poses a serious threat to stored maize, necessitating effective management strategies. The investigation of safer alternatives is necessary, as chemical control techniques pose health and environmental hazards despite their widespread use. The efficacy of indigenous spice powder in powder form as potential grain protectants against *S. zeamais* infestation was evaluated in this study. The objective of this investigation was to evaluate the feasibility of these alternatives for the management of *S. zeamais*, which encompassed adult mortality, adult emergence, and weight loss. The maize weevil was managed in this experiment by employing six distinct spices and one pesticide, viz., chili, turmeric, coriander, garlic, cumin, black pepper, chemical (carbaryl), and untreated control. At a concentration of 2 g/100 g of grain, black pepper exhibited superior performance in adult mortality, adult emergence, and grain weight loss reduction. At the same dosage, turmeric exhibited better efficacy in adult mortality, adult emergence, and grain weight reduction. Based on the toxic effect, the superiority of spices as protection materials against the maize weevil was ranked as black pepper powder, turmeric powder, cumin powder, garlic powder, chili powder, and coriander powder, respectively. The findings emphasized spices' potential as viable alternatives for preserving stored grains. Botanical insecticides (Spices) provide environmentally favorable solutions; however, additional research is necessary to determine their optimal dosages.

KEYWORDS

Carbaryl, maize weevil, *Piper nigrum*, *Sitophilus zeamais*, spices

1. INTRODUCTION

Maize (*Zea mays* L.), belonging to the family Gramineae, is the third most important cereal crop globally after wheat and rice (Erenstein et al., 2022). Although it occupies less land than either of these crops, maize boasts a higher average yield per hectare, producing approximately 5.5 tons per hectare (Islam et al., 2022). Maize is highly nutritious, containing about 70-72% digestible carbohydrates, 4-4.5% fats and oils, and 9.5-11% protein. Additionally, maize kernels are rich in vitamins and fats, making them a strong energy source comparable to root and tuber crops (Siregar et al., 2024). Globally, around 66% of maize for livestock feed, 25% for human consumption, and 9% for industrial applications are used by populations. In developing nations, approximately 50% of maize is consumed by humans, 43% by livestock, and the remaining amount is used for industrial purposes (Hou et al., 2024).

Maize, however, is susceptible to various insect pests, particularly during storage, with the maize weevil being the most destructive pest (CUI et al., 2024). This pest can cause up to 50% losses during storage, particularly in tropical climates where temperature and humidity levels rise in the summer (Simon et al., 2023). The maize weevil is a significant pest in stored grain, and various methods are used worldwide to control it. Synthetic insecticides are commonly employed, especially for stored product pests. However, excessive use of these synthetic chemicals can lead to severe health and environmental concerns, such as insect resistance, food contamination, pest resurgence, and harm to non-target organisms (Song et al., 2023). Therefore, there is a pressing need for

alternative organic pest control methods that are affordable, environmentally friendly, and less toxic (Jyosthna et al., 2023).

Researchers and farmers have noted the effectiveness of plant-based materials, including spices and plant powders, in controlling insect pests (Guo et al., 2023). Recently, there has been increased interest in using natural products for pest management due to their lower environmental impact and reduced toxicity to mammals (Feng et al., 2020). Spices, widely used in culinary applications worldwide, are considered safe for humans and pose fewer risks than non-edible plants when used as insecticides. They are also cost-effective, easily accessible, and safe to use in stored grains (Ghosh et al., 2020). Farmers can cheaply produce these plant-based extracts for use, making them a practical and sustainable option for pest management. Integrating insecticidal natural products from locally available plants offers a safe and promising alternative (Babu et al., 2020).

For decades, chemical insecticides have been extensively used in grain storage facilities to manage insect pests. However, because of their residual properties, these chemicals have posed significant risks to the environment and consumers. Therefore, the development of alternative, eco-friendly pest management solutions has become critical. Eco-friendly pest management strategies leverage the natural defenses that plants and trees have developed over millennia to protect themselves from insects and pathogens. In the present study, we evaluated the efficacy of various spice powders in controlling *S. zeamais* infestations, aiming to reduce environmental pollution, limit residual effects, and prevent grain contamination. These efforts are expected to contribute to the sustainable

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management of maize pests while ensuring satisfactory storage conditions for farmers. The objectives of this study are to assess the effectiveness of spice powders in reducing *S. zeamais* infestations and identify eco-friendly alternatives to toxic chemical pesticides for maize weevil management.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Experimental setup

An experiment on eco-friendly management of the maize weevil (*Sitophilus zeamais*) was conducted in the Entomology Department laboratory at Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh, from June 2023 to February 2024. The study evaluated six different spice powders and one pesticide for maize weevil control. The experiment used maize grains, specifically the Savar variety, as a susceptible host for maize weevils (*Sitophilus zeamais*). Six spice powders, were tested at a dosage of 2g per 100g of grain, while the insecticide as a treatment was applied at 0.5g per 100g.

Table 1: The details of the spices and pesticide, including their names, scientific names, families, and forms used

Type	Common name	Scientific Name	Family	Used form
Spices forms	Chili	<i>Capsicum annuum</i>	Solanaceae	Powder
	Turmeric	<i>Curcuma longa</i>	Zingiberaceae	
	Coriander	<i>Coriandrum sativum</i>	Apiaceae	
	Garlic	<i>Allium sativum</i>	Amaryllidaceae	
	Cumin	<i>Cuminum cyminum</i>	Apiaceae	
	Black pepper	<i>Piper nigrum</i>	Piperaceae	
Pesticide	Name of the pesticide	Group	Dose	Powder
	Seven Star Abin 85 SP	Carbaryl	0.05g/100g grain	

Spice plant parts were collected from the local market near Bangladesh Agricultural University. Fresh spices were collected from a local market near Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh. After sun drying for five days, garlic was chopped and dried for seven days to reduce moisture, followed by oven drying at 100°C for two hours to achieve a fine powder. All spice powders were ground and sieved through a 40-mesh sieve for fine dust and stored in airtight containers. Seven Star Abin 85 WP was used as a chemical insecticide; its active ingredient was carbaryl in this study. Carbaryl pesticide was obtained from a licensed shop, and fresh maize grains were sourced from Mymensingh's local market for comparison with the spices' effectiveness.

Figure 1: Species and chemical (Carbaryl) are powdered form

Maize weevils were collected from a local household near Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh, and reared for over two months (June-August 2023) in plastic jars under favorable conditions. Temperatures between 25°C and 32°C and 70-90% relative humidity were

maintained to promote rapid weevil development and reproduction. The jars were covered with perforated cloth for air circulation and to prevent weevils from escaping. The Savar maize variety was used as their food source, and the weevil population increased significantly due to the high temperatures, with regular checks conducted at intervals.

Figure 2: Rearing of maize weevil and applying treatment on each replication

2.2 Data Collection

Data were collected at 3 DAT, 6 DAT, 9 DAT, and 12 DAT to monitor maize weevil mortality in each treatment. The mortality of the parent weevils was recorded from the 1st to the 15th day after their release. When nearly all of the insects in each treatment had died, monitoring ceased. Adult mortality was counted daily. And over all, the total count of deaths in the treatment condition was compared with the untreated condition, and we calculated the percentage of adult mortality in the treated condition by following the same formula as before. The formula is given below:

$$\% \text{ Morality} = \frac{\text{Total number of dead maize weevil}}{\text{Total number of maize weevils released}} \times 100$$

After a few days, we monitored adult emergence rates daily for 10 DAT, 20 DAT, 30 DAT, and 40 DAT, and it started from the first emergence. 28 days after release, the maize weevils began emerging. Larvae and pupae fed inside maize kernels, and as they matured, they bore holes in the kernels to emerge. The number of emerging adult maize weevils was counted daily from the date of the first emergence. The weight losses were caused by the feeding of larvae inside the seeds. After almost 5 months of starting the experiment, we finally measured the weight loss of grain in each treatment, each replication. The weight loss was measured by using a digital balance. The percentage of infestation has been calculated by the formula below:

$$\% \text{ Grain weight loss} = \frac{\text{Initial weight} - \text{final weight}}{\text{Initial weight}} \times 100$$

2.3 Statistical Analysis

The experiments were conducted in a completely randomized design. The data were analyzed using Statistix 10 (Version 10.0 Analytical Software USA), and mean values were separated by DMRT and least significant difference (LSD).

3. RESULTS

The mean mortality percent of adult maize weevils was substantially influenced by eight different treatments, with a mean mortality rate that ranged from 6.80% to 100%. Within three days, the chemical control (Carbaryl) resulted in a 100% mean mortality rate. Black pepper was the most effective spice treatment (89.20%) in terms of mortality (Figure 3). As the time intervals increased, the cumulative mortality of maize weevils increased significantly in all treatments. After three days after applied treatment (3 DAT), the lowest cumulative mortality rate was observed in chemical control (10%) followed by turmeric (7.2%), and the lowest was in control (0%) treatment. At 6 DAT, it was revealed that the maximal cumulative mortality had been recorded in chemical treatment (10%) followed by black pepper (9), turmeric (8.4), and cumin (7.6%), respectively. At 9, 12, and 15 DAT, the maximum percent of cumulative mortality was observed in chemical treatment (10%), followed by turmeric with a value of 9.4% in 9 DAT, 9.6% in 12 DAT, and 9.8% in 15 DAT (Figure 4). Distinct spices and chemicals (Carbaryl) were statistically varied based on the mean number of adult emergences of Maize weevil (*Sitophilus zeamais* L.) The greatest number of mean adult emergences occurred by the untreated control treatment (24.40). No adult emergence was detected in the extent of chemical treatment (Figure 5). Among spice treatments, coriander had a higher mean adult emergence (16.15) and black pepper had a reduced mean adult emergence (2.30).

Figure 3: Effect of different treatments on adult mortality (%) at 15 days after insect release

Figure 4: Cumulative mortality (Number) by different treatments

The control treatment had the highest cumulative adult emergence (5.2) at 10 DAT, followed by garlic (3.4), and additionally, it was observed that both black pepper and turmeric had minimal cumulative adult emergence (0.6). The control treatment had the highest cumulative adult emergence

at 20, 30, and 40 DAT, with numbers of 21, 32.6, and 38.8, respectively. In the instance of chemical treatment, no cumulative adult emergence was observed (Figure 6).

Figure 5: Effect of different treatments on mean adult emergence

Figure 6: Effect of different treatments on cumulative adult emergence (Number)

The weight loss of maize grain varied substantially among various spices and chemical treatments. No weight loss was observed in the chemical (carbaryl) treatment, and the untreated control exhibited the maximum mean weight loss (2.99 g). It was noted that the minimal mean weight loss had recorded in black pepper with the quantity of 0.304 g, followed by turmeric (0.482 g) and chili (0.730 g), respectively (Figure 7). The

chemical treatment did not result in any weight loss. Black pepper demonstrated the lowest weight loss of 1.52% among spice treatments, while turmeric exhibited the second lowest weight loss of 2.41% (Figure 8).

Figure 7: Effect of different treatments on grain weight loss (g)

Figure 8: Effect of treatments on grain weight loss (%)

4. DISCUSSION

Constitutive compounds, such as essential oils and chemicals of different spices, performed as a potential source of botanical or organic insecticides that can eradicate various insects and pests from injured or targeted plants, thus preventing insects from remaining longer on the crop. Black pepper powder is the most effective treatment among all spices, with the highest mortality rate in a short period of time. For the potency material in pepper seed powdery substances, insects perished swiftly, and in addition, F1 generation also lessened. 1 g of black pepper powder applied per 100 g of corn kernels has proven useful for removing *Sitophilus* spp., resulting in mortality rates that range up to 80% (Arrahman et al., 2020). Turmeric also exhibited a high mortality rate. Pepper seed powder raises the mean mortality of rice weevils more than other spices in powdered form, and chili fruit powder possesses the smallest impact compared to turmeric, lemongrass, and cinnamon (Imran et al., 2021). The cowpea seeds treated with *P. nigrum* seed methanol extract had a 100% mortality rate within 48 hours (Niranjana and Samanthikka, 2022). Maize weevil mortality increased as the time intervals in all treatments increased. These observations coincided with the outcomes of Hikal et al., in 2017. A study in 2009 asserted that using black pepper powdery substances with a concentration of 0.5% (w/w) could eradicate 90% of *S. granarius* species within 5 days (Ashouri and Shayesteh, 2009). Turmeric and black pepper extracts were moderately repellent in nature and worked relatively quickly, whereas lemongrass and dried chili extracts had a mild attractant capacity (Ishii et al., 2010). Researchers observed that the minimal percent of adult emergence (11.11%) was measured in black pepper treatment (Islam et al., 2013). Immediately after the application of 2% black pepper seed powder significantly revealed as the best treatment in comparison to others and triggered 100% mortality within one day, and moreover, different concentrations of black pepper seed powder impacted the mortality, oviposition, adult emergence, and seed weight loss of *C. maculatus* (Govindan et al., 2023). A study in 2011 confirmed that *P. guineense* powder produced substantially more effective outcomes, resulting in a limited number of damaged seeds and wounds per seed (Udo et al., 2011). Researchers experimented that the 4 g of black paper powder gave considerably the highest mortality of cowpea weevil at the mean numbers of insects (45) and as well exhibited the lowest level of weight loss at the mean numbers (5) (Abdihamid et al., 2023). The chemical (carbaryl) treatments produced no weight loss, but the untreated control had the greatest mean weight reduction.

5. CONCLUSION

The chemical treatment (carbaryl) resulted in little adult mortality and weight loss. However, this kind of chemical is not an eco-friendly management strategy for controlling the maize weevil. Considering factors such as high mortality, less adult emergence, and less weight loss, black pepper powder reveals the best performance, and the second-best results are shown by turmeric powder among the tested treatment options.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

All authors declared there was no conflict of interests.

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